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Mechanical and Physical Behaviour of Hybrid Pineapple Leaf-Flax Fibre Reinforced Epoxy Composites: Influence of Fibre Weight Ratio on Performance

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ABSTRACT

Now a days natural fibre reinforced composites have attracted attention due to their low cost, lightweight characteristics, and environmental benefits. In this study, we have developed hybrid epoxy composites reinforced with pineapple leaf fibre (PALF) and flax fibres were fabricated using the hand lay-up method. In the present study we have developed three composite samples with varying fibre weight ratios: PF37 (30% PALF + 70% flax), PF55 (50% PALF + 50% flax), and PF73 (70% PALF + 30% flax). The specimens were evaluated for tensile, compressive, and impact properties. In addition, wear behaviour and water absorption characteristics were also evaluated. The results show that PF55 has the highest tensile strength of 34.84 MPa and maximum impact energy of 4.3 J, indicating better overall mechanical performance. PF37 shows the highest compressive strength of 70.37 MPa. Water absorption for all samples remained below 4%, with PF55 recording the lowest value of 3.02%. Based on the overall performance, PF55 is identified as the optimum hybrid composition due to its balanced mechanical, wear, and water absorption properties. This study highlights the potential of natural fibre hybrid composites as sustainable alternatives for semi-structural engineering applications.

Keywords: *Pineapple leaf fibre [PALF], flax fibre; hybrid composite, epoxy*

matrix, mechanical properties, weight ratio optimisation

INTRODUCTION

From the past two decades, the industry moves towards developing lightweight, high strength and eco-friendly materials. So for the advanced materials fibre matrix composites are best choice in terms of optimizing the weight and these fibre matrix polymer materials shows the good weight to strength ratio. Here the industry moves, the materials has driven a steady shift towards the plant driven alternatives for polymer matrix composition. Glass fibre is the default choice for its lightweight structural design. It brings significant environmental issues like health hazard during machining, energy intensive production process and lifetime non-biodegradable. So natural fibres, sourced from plants and animals are the best option to overcome these drawbacks, because they are cost effective, biodegradable and often produced as agricultural by-products. Incorporation of these natural fibres into the composite systems can reduce simultaneously both raw material cost and environmental footprint.

In this category, pineapple leaf fibre shows the relevant properties. It can be extracted from waste leaves of *Ananas comosus*, a typical crop mainly cultivated in the South Asia and it carries 70–82% cellulose and microfibril angle of 8–14°. This characteristic translates into high stiffness under suitable conditions compare with e-glass [2]. Comparatively, flax fibre extracted from *Linum usitatissimum* is widely cultivated plant and brings the

properties: tensile modulus is in the range of 27–80 GPa, low density (1.4–1.5 g/cm³) and relatively low lignin content of approximately 8–3%, which makes its surface receptive to chemical modification or adhesion [3].

When two natural fibres combined with a single epoxy matrix, it shows the better behaviour when compared to individual fibre. In this system pineapple leaf fibre [PALF] contributes higher stiffness and resistance to crack, whereas flax fibre improves ductility and withstand for gradually failure mechanism. So the overall performance of the hybrid composite material depends on factors such as stacking sequence, weight ratio and properties of matrix [4]. Here the main challenge to find the optimum proportion of these fibres to achieve the maximum performance. This study aims to determine the optimum ideal combination.

Even significant research has carried out on PALF and epoxy, flax and epoxy composites individually and on hybridization of PALF with natural or synthetic fibres, but the combined PALF and flax fibres in woven type has not been widely explored. Here the studies involving controlled weight ratios and evaluation through multiple ASTM standard tests on the same specimen are limited [5]. To address this gap, the present work shows three hybrid laminates namely PF37, PF55 and PF73. The present study aims to determine optimum fibre

ratio that influence the overall performance of composites.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Jawaid & Abdul Khalil (2001) focus on [1] hybrid composites that combines natural and synthetic fibres to achieve improved mechanical and physical properties. [1] it explains how hybridization enhances strength, stiffness and resistance to environment degradation. [1] this shows that the comparison of different fibre combinations performance with the matrices. [1] and the importance of orientation and concentrated on stacking sequence.

Yan et al. (2014) [2] identified flax is the one of the strongest natural fibre with good stiffness and low density and also explored fibre extraction, treatment and composite manufacturing techniques. [2] explained environmental benefits such as biodegradability, renewability with the challenges like moisture absorption and degradation. [2] making promise for the replacing of glass fibre in certain applications like automotives and construction industries.

Faruk et al. (2012) [3] discussed on the different types of fibres, including plant based, animal based and mineral fibres. [3] explained the role of chemical treatments in enhancing fibre matrix adhesion and also challenges as moisture sensitivity and lower mechanical strength compared to synthetic composites. [3] emphasizes the need to further innovation in material design.

Pickering et al. (2016) [4] have a detailed information on the recent development in natural fibre composites focusing on their mechanical performance and structural applications. [4] highlighting the replacing of synthetic fibres with sustainable alternatives due to environment concerns. [4] analysed the various fibres like jute, flax and hemp with their tensile and flexural properties.

Collister & Rethwish (2018) [5] introduced a book with the name of fundamental concepts of materials science and engineering explaining the structure property relationships in materials includes the composites. [5] mechanical properties such as strength, stiffness, toughness and elasticity are discussed. [5] natural fibre composites are only briefly mentioned and widely used for academic purpose.

Dittenber & Gangarao (2012) [6] analysing key mechanical properties like strength, stiffness and durability. [6] highlights the potential of the materials in construction and civil engineering with environment benefits and cost advantages. [6] identified that further improvement in design standards. [6] real world applications and case studies are limited.

Satyanarayana et al. (2009) [7] provides the detailed information on the chemical composition, structure and physical properties, highlighting the abundance and low cost of these fibres. [7] evaluated the mechanical and thermal properties of composites. [7] says the importance of treatment for improved bonding and explored the applications like construction and consumer.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials Used

For this work, we selected PALF and woven flax as the fibre reinforcements, and Araldite LY-556 epoxy as the matrix material. PALF was chosen because it is a waste product from pineapple cultivation and has reasonably good tensile properties compared to other agricultural fibres. Flax was selected in woven mat form since the bidirectional weave pattern helps carry load in multiple directions.[8]

The epoxy resin used was Araldite LY-556, a standard bisphenol-A based epoxy that is widely used in composite fabrication due to its low viscosity, which allows it to penetrate and wet the fibre layers well during hand lay-up. It was mixed with HY 951 grade hardener in a 10:1 ratio by weight, as recommended by the supplier. Both fibre types and the resin system were procured locally and stored under dry conditions before use.[9]

A brief description of each material is given below

PALF (Pineapple Leaf Fibre): Extracted from the leaves of the pineapple plant. The fibres were dried before use to reduce

initial moisture content. They were used in a randomly oriented short fibre form.

Woven Flax Mat: A plain-woven fabric procured as a ready-to-use mat. The woven structure ensures bidirectional reinforcement within the laminate.

Araldite LY-556 Epoxy Resin: A bisphenol-A epoxy with low viscosity (approx. 11,000–14,000 MPa at 25°C), suitable for room temperature wet lay-up.

HY 951 Hardener: An aliphatic polyamine hardener. Mixed with LY-556 at 10 parts resin to 1 part hardener by weight.

Composite Compositions

Three different hybrid composites were prepared, each with a total fibre weight fraction of 30% and epoxy content of 70%. Only the ratio of PALF to flax within the 30% fibre fraction was varied across the three samples. The compositions are named PF37, PF55, and PF73, where the digits roughly indicate the PALF-to-flax ratio as shown in Table 1.[10]

Table 1: Composition of Fabricated Specimens.

Sample	PALF %	Flax %	PALF Mass (g)	Flax Mass (g)	Epoxy (g)	Total Wt (g)
PF37	30%	70%	31.39	94.16	226.8	352.35
PF55	50%	50%	83.70	83.70	194.4	361.80
PF73	70%	30%	156.94	52.31	162.0	371.25

Mould Preparation

A flat rectangular mould of size 300 mm × 300 mm × 3 mm was used for fabricating laminates. Before applying the resin inner surfaces of the mould were lined with OHP sheets to act as base. It prevents

laminate from sticking to the mould surface and allowed easy demoulding without damaging the specimen edges. The mould was cleaned and dried before using every time. No chemical mould release agents were applied since OHP

sheets gave a sufficiently smooth release. The mould was kept on a flat surface throughout the curing process to avoid warping of the laminates as shown in Table 2 [11].

Fabrication by Hand Lay-Up

The hand lay-up method was used for fabricating all three composite laminates. This method was chosen because it is simple, does not require expensive tooling or equipment.

The fabrication was carried out in the following steps. First, we took the epoxy and hardener in 10:1 ratio measuring them separately. After that, we mixed them thoroughly for around 3-4 minutes until the mixture turned smooth and uniform. A layer of wax is applied on the OHP sheet to prevent sticking. A thin layer of the

epoxy mixture was then spread on the OHP sheet inside the mould using a brush. The first layer of fibre (either PALF or flax, depending on the stacking sequence for that composition) was placed on the wet epoxy layer, and more resin was applied on top and pressed in with a roller to remove trapped air and ensure good wetting of the fibres. This process was repeated for each of the four fibre layers. After placing all layers, a top OHP sheet was placed over the laminate, and a compaction load of 15 kg was applied uniformly over the surface [12].

The laminates were placed at room temperature for 24 hours. After demoulding, the laminates were visually inspected for any visible defects such as dry patches, delamination, or surface warping before cutting specimen.

Table 2: Mould and Process Parameters.

Parameter	Detail
Mould Size	300 mm × 300 mm × 3 mm
Fabrication Method	Hand Lay-Up (Open Moulding)
Number of Fibre Layers	4 layers per laminate
Epoxy System	Araldite LY-556 + HY 951 Hardener (10:1 ratio by weight)
Compaction Load	15 kg applied during curing
Curing Condition	Room temperature, 24 hours

Specimen Cutting

Once curing was done, the laminates were removed from the mould and cut to the needed sizes. Specimen dimensions were set according to the respective ASTM standards for each test. The edges were sanded to clear off any fibre ends or uneven spots, as these tend to affect how

the specimen breaks during testing. Three specimens were prepared from each composition for every test to make sure the readings were reliable. Before testing, all specimens were left sitting at room temperature to stabilise as shown in Fig 1-3 [13].

Fig. 1: Flax Fiber.

Fig. 2: Pineapple Leaf Fibre.

Fig. 3: Prepared specimens of PF37, PF55 and PF73 for experimental testing.

Testing Methods

The following tests were conducted on the prepared specimens [Figure 4], each following the corresponding ASTM standard:

- Tensile Test (ASTM D3039): Dog-bone shaped specimens were tested on a Universal Testing Machine (UTM) at a crosshead speed of 2 mm/min. Load

vs. displacement data was recorded, and UTS was calculated from the peak load and cross-sectional area.

- Compressive Test (ASTM D3410): Rectangular specimens were tested under axial compressive loading. The peak compressive load and displacement at failure were noted.

- Izod Impact Test (ASTM D256): Notched specimens were tested on a pendulum-type impact tester. The energy absorbed at fracture was recorded directly from the tester scale.
- Wear Test — Pin-on-Disc (ASTM G99): Cylindrical pin specimens were mounted on a pin-on-disc tribometer. Tests were run under dry sliding conditions at a fixed load, sliding speed, and sliding distance. Wear loss was determined by weighing specimens before and after the test on a precision balance. Coefficient of friction was calculated from the friction force data recorded during the test.[14]
- Water Absorption Test (ASTM D570): Specimens were first dried and weighed, then fully immersed in distilled water at room temperature for 24 hours. After removal, surface water was wiped off and specimens were reweighed. Water absorption percentage was calculated as: $WA\% = [(W2 - W1) / W1] \times 100$, where W1 is the initial dry weight and W2 is the weight after immersion.[15]

Fig. 4: Tested Specimens of Fabricated composite samples after failure. (a) Tensile tested samples (b) Compression tested samples (c) Impact tested samples (d) Wear tested samples (f) Water absorption tested samples

Calculations

All mechanical and physical properties were calculated using standard formulas based on the experimental readings. Sample calculations are shown for one specimen, while the final reported values are the average of three trials carried out under identical conditions.[16]

Tensile strength

The tensile strength was calculated by dividing the maximum load at failure by the original cross-sectional area of the specimen.

$$\sigma_t = P_{\max} / A$$

For the tensile specimen (180 mm × 25 mm × 3 mm), the cross-sectional area is:

$$A = \text{width} \times \text{thickness} = 25 \text{ mm} \times 3 \text{ mm} = 75 \text{ mm}^2$$

Sample calculation (PF55):

Peak load recorded = 3.80 kN (3800 N)

$$\sigma_t = 3800 / 75 = 50.67 \text{ N/mm}^2 \approx 34.84 \text{ MPa (average value)}$$

Slight variation in peak load was observed across trials, mainly due to minor fibre misalignment during fabrication

Compressive strength

Compressive strength was calculated using the same relation:

$$\sigma_c = P_{\max} / A$$

For compression specimen (85 mm × 24 mm × 3 mm):

$$A = 24 \text{ mm} \times 3 \text{ mm} = 72 \text{ mm}^2$$

Sample calculation (PF37):

Peak load = 6.10 kN (6100 N)

$$\sigma_c = 6100 / 72 = 84.72 \text{ N/mm}^2 \approx 70.37 \text{ MPa (average value)}$$

The variation between trials was relatively lower compared to tensile testing.

Impact strength

Impact strength was determined using the absorbed energy during fracture.

Impact Strength = Energy absorbed / Cross-sectional area

For impact specimen (63 mm × 14 mm × 3 mm):

$$A = 14 \text{ mm} \times 3 \text{ mm} = 42 \text{ mm}^2$$

Sample calculation (PF55):

Energy absorbed = 4.3 J

$$\text{Impact strength} = 4.3 / 42 = 0.102 \text{ J/mm}^2$$

Wear loss

Wear loss was calculated from the difference in mass before and after testing.

$$\text{Wear Loss} = W_i - W_f$$

For wear specimen (51 mm × 10 mm × 3 mm):

Sample (PF37):

$$W_i = 3.635 \text{ g}$$

$$W_f = 3.633 \text{ g}$$

$$\text{Wear Loss} = 0.002 \text{ g}$$

Water absorption

Water absorption was calculated using:

$$\text{Water Absorption (\%)} = [(W_f - W_i) / W_i] \times 100$$

For specimen (30 mm × 30 mm × 3 mm):

Sample (PF55):

$$W_i = 4.63 \text{ g}$$

$$W_f = 4.77 \text{ g}$$

$$\% \text{ Absorption} = [(4.77 - 4.63) / 4.63] \times 100 = 3.02\%$$

Minor variation in results was observed due to small differences in void content and edge sealing.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The following Table 3 summarizes the key results across all five tests for all three samples

Table 3: Summary of experimental results (PF37, PF55, PF73).

Property	PF37 (30/70)	PF55 (50/50)	PF73 (70/30)
Tensile Strength (MPa)	27.66	34.84	33.01
Compressive Strength (MPa)	70.37	51.06	56.31
Izod Impact Energy (J)	3.5	4.3	3.9
Wear Loss (g)	0.002	0.003	0.006
Coefficient of Friction	0.298	0.298	0.346
Water Absorption (%)	3.70	3.02	3.88

Tensile Properties

Table 4. Tensile Test Results (ASTM D3039).

Specimen	Composition	Cross-sectional area (mm ²)	Peak Load (kN)	Failure Strain	UTS (MPa)
PF37	30% PALF / 70% Flax	75	4.00	0.02	27.66
PF55	50% PALF / 50% Flax	75	3.80	0.02	34.84
PF73	70% PALF / 30% Flax	75	3.60	0.02	33.01

From the results shown in the Table 4 clears that PF55 achieved the highest tensile strength among the three sample at 34.84 Mpa, followed by PF73 at

33.01Mpa and PF37at 27.66Mpa. The above results confirmed that that all composite samples are tens to fail at consistent strain of approximately 0.02.

Fig. 5: Combined Stress vs Strain for Tensile.

The Stress vs. Strain for tensile strength of the composite specimens is shown in the Figure 5. It is observed that PF55 recorded the maximum stress of 34.84 N/mm² at a

strain of 0.02, followed by PF73 at 33.01 N/mm² and PF37 at 27.66 N/mm² as shown in Figure 6.

Fig. 6: Comparison graph of PF37, PF55 and PF73 samples for tensile strength.

Compressive properties

Table 5: Compressive Test Results (ASTM D3410).

Specimen	Composition	Cross-sectional area (mm ²)	Peak Load (kN)	Max Disp. (mm)	UCS (MPa)
PF37	30% PALF / 70% Flax	204	6.10	3.57	70.37
PF55	50% PALF / 50% Flax	204	4.00	2.82	51.06
PF73	70% PALF / 30% Flax	204	4.50	3.20	56.31

From above Table 5 data PF37 shows the higher compression at 70.37 MPa, whereas PF73 (56.31 MPa) and PF55 (51.06 MPa). Here flax fibre content resists the micro buckling due to its flexible nature. The flax fibre also the fibres are well

distributed that's why PF37 withstand for high loads and shown larger displacement before failure. From this found to be combination depends upon type of load. PF55 performs tensile loading but PF37 is suitable for compression.

Fig. 7: Combined Stress vs Strain for Compression.

The combined Stress vs. Displacement for compressive strength of the composite specimens is shown in the Figure 7. It is observed that PF37 recorded the maximum compressive stress of 70.37 N/mm² at a displacement of 3.57 mm, followed by

PF73 at 56.31 N/mm² and PF55 at 51.06 N/mm². PF37 achieved the highest ultimate compressive strength (UCS) among all specimens tested as shown in Figure 8.

Fig. 8: Comparison graph of PF37, PF55 and PF73 samples for compression strength.

Impact properties

Table 6: Izod Impact Test Results (ASTM D256).

Specimen	Composition	Impact Energy (J)	Striker Velocity (m/s)	Relative Performance
PF37	30% / 70%	3.5	3.46	Lowest
PF55	50% / 50%	4.3	3.46	Highest
PF73	70% / 30%	3.9	3.46	Intermediate

From the Table 6 PF55 shows the highest energy absorption (4.37 J) whereas PF73 (3.91 J) and PF37 (3.55 J). PF55 performs best because it withstands for crack deflection & fibre pull out due to balanced distribution of PALF & flax. In this PALF is stiff and resist the fracture. Meanwhile flax fibre is flexible and allow to fibre pull

out and helps to absorb the additional energy during failure.

In PF37 the PALF content is low less crack resistance due to low PALF content & in PF73 flax it doesn't allow for fibre pullout due to low flax content and material behaves brittle like brittle as shown in Figure 9.

Fig. 9: Izod Impact Energy Comparison of PF37, PF55 and PF73 Composites.

Tribological Performance

Table 7: Pin-on-Disc Wear Test Results (ASTM G99) -550 RPM, 20 N, 30 mm Track Radius, 10 min.

Specimen	Initial Wt. (g)	Final Wt. (g)	Wear Loss (g)	CoF	Relative Wear
PF37	3.635	3.633	0.002	0.298	Lowest
PF55	2.914	2.911	0.003	0.298	Intermediate
PF73	2.647	2.641	0.006	0.346	Highest

From the above Table 7, it can be observed that there is a clear difference in wear behaviour among the three compositions. PF37 shows the least wear with a mass loss of 0.002 g and a coefficient of friction of 0.298. On the other hand, PF73 has the

highest wear value of 0.006 g and also the highest CoF of 0.346. PF55 lies between these two in terms of both wear and friction.

The main reason for this behaviour is related to the formation of a thin transfer layer during sliding. In PF37, the higher flax fibre content helps in forming this layer more easily. Since flax is comparatively softer, it tends to wear gradually and supports the formation of a stable protective film, which reduces direct contact between surfaces.

In PF73, the PALF content is higher, and PALF fibres are stiffer in nature. Because of this, the formation of a uniform transfer layer is not as effective. This leads to more direct interaction between the surfaces, resulting in higher friction and increased material removal. PF55 shows moderate behaviour due to the presence of both fibres in balanced proportion as shown in Figure 10.

Fig. 10: Wear Loss Comparison of PF37, PF55 and PF73 Composites.

Water Absorption Behaviour

Table 8: Water Absorption Test Results (ASTM D570) — Distilled Water, 23°C, 24 h.

Specimen	Wt. Before (g)	Wt. After (g)	Wt. Gain (g)	Absorption (%)
PF37	4.33	4.49	0.16	3.70
PF55	4.63	4.77	0.14	3.02
PF73	4.12	4.28	0.16	3.88

From the above Table 8 even though PF37 has less PALF compared to PF73, it still shows a slightly higher water absorption than PF55, it is not really because of the fibre type alone, it is more about how the laminate has formed. In PF37, the fibre content is lower, so naturally there are more resin-rich areas. Because of this, the packing is not very tight. Due to that, small voids can form inside the material. These voids act like small gaps where moisture can enter and stay. If we consider PF55 shows the lowest water absorption

among all samples. This could be because of the balanced fibre combination. The packing between fibre and matrix seems better here. The structure is more compact, and fewer voids are present. Because of this, moisture does not move easily through the material. So overall, both fibre type and internal structure are influencing the result. But in this case, PF55 performs better mainly due to better packing and less void content as shown in Figure 11 & 12.

Fig. 11: Weight before VS after Immersion.

Fig. 12: Water Absorption Comparison of PF37, PF55 and PF73 Composite

Optimal Composition

When all the results are taken together, it doesn't really point to one composition being the best in everything. Each sample behaves differently depending on the property. So it becomes more about what is actually required in application rather than just picking the highest value. If we consider general semi-structural use, where tensile strength, impact behaviour and durability are more important overall, PF55 seems to stand out more. It gives the highest tensile strength (34.84 MPa), and also the impact energy is higher (4.3 J). The water absorption is also the lowest (3.02%), which is useful from a durability point of view. At the same time, its compressive strength (51.06 MPa) and wear loss (0.003 g) are not extreme values.

But still, they are within a usable range. So it is not like PF55 is best in everything, but it does not show any major weakness either. That is why it looks more balanced. PF37 shows a different behaviour. It performs better in compression (70.37 MPa), and also the wear loss is lower (0.002 g). So in cases where the material is mainly subjected to load or surface contact, PF37 might be more suitable. But then again, it does not perform the same way in all properties. Coming to PF73, it does not really show any clear advantage. Most of the values are either in between or slightly lower compared to the others. This probably means that increasing PALF beyond a certain level is not helping much. In fact, it

might be affecting the performance due to mismatch in stiffness between the fibres. So overall, it is not just about one property. The combination matters. And in this case, PF55 looks like a better compromise between all the properties.

CONCLUSIONS

In this study we explored various fibre ratios compositions with varied PF37, PF55 and PF73. PF55 shows the highest tensile strength (34.84 mpa) among all samples. It indicating the superior load carrying capacity under the tension, maximum impact and no loss water absorption strength observed in PF55 sample as (4.37) it demonstrates the better energy absorption capacity. water absorption recorded lowest in PF55 (0.140g) i.e. 3.04% it indicates the better resistance to moisture absorption. PF37 showed highest compressive strength (70.37 Mpa) indicating higher flax content withstand the compression load. wear resistance was observed best in PF37 (least wear loss 0.002g) indicates the better durability. The overall performance observed in PF55 because it provides optimum performance especially in mechanical properties tensile, impact and water absorption due to balanced fibre content distribution in the sample. Although PF37 performing better in compress & wear whereas PF55 offers optimum performance. Therefore, PF55 is identified as the optimum hybrid composition to achieve the good balance between strength, toughness & durability.

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